

**RISK FACTORS FOR ISOLATED SYSTOLIC ARTERIAL
HYPERTENSION IN A FARMING POPULATION (SCREENING
RESULTS)**

Mamasoliev N.S.¹

Nishonova N.A.²

Kalandarov D.M.³

Abduvakhopova N.R.⁴

¹⁻²⁻³⁻⁴Andijan State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514516>

The aim of the study was to identify and evaluate the risk factors of isolated arterial hypertension (AH) in the farming population (FP) of Uzbekistan.

Research material and methods. 1069 male and female population > 18-70 years old were involved in special screening. This farming population was examined using epidemiological, clinical, biochemical and instrumental methods in the conditions of the Fergana Valley. Arterial hypertension risk factors are diagnosed according to generally accepted criteria (WHO, 2018).

Obtained results and conclusions. In the farming population (FP) isolated systolic arterial hypertension (ISAH) is diagnosed with a 9.2% increase due to family risk factors. In the farming population (FP) with higher education - 3.3% (in men - 2.3% and in women - 5.0%; $p < 0.05$), in those with secondary education - 2.5% (in men - 2.4% and 2.7% in women; $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.05$), in divorcees - 2.2% (in men - 0.00% and in women - 4.8%; $p < 0.4$) and in widows 7.7% (14.3% in men and 5.3% in women; $p < 0.01$) are identified with scattering frequencies. In age-related cases, a doubling of the frequency is observed. Although these results are low in comparison with the epidemiological indicators obtained in other populations and on an international scale, preventive medicine should not be neglected.